

THE IMPACT OF DIFFERENTIATED LESSON PLANNING ON STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

This study explores possible implementations of differentiated strategies for the whole lesson plan and its effect on classroom management. The findings reveal that, due to the widespread use of differentiated lesson plan and different activities for diverse level show the more positive understanding of language and increased students' autonomy in the role of classroom management. The impact of differentiated lesson planning can play a pivotal role in language classrooms since it endeavors to vary teachers' teaching methods and assessing tools. Therefore, increased learners' participation and more fast-paced learning environment can motive instructors to increase their time management skills as long as improving students' anxiety level. The results demonstrate that differentiated lesson planning is more comprehensible and convincing comparing with traditional single way of instruction along with traditional way of single lesson plan. These can conclude that integrating differentiated instruction into lesson planning technologies into EFL methodology can create more supportive and student-oriented language environment.

Key words: Differentiated instruction, Needs assessment, bio-modal distribution, ongoing assessment, comprehensible input, professional growth

The bio-modal distribution of students from diverse cultural, economic, and social backgrounds leads to minimize student performance [3]. It is nowadays fairly frequently to see the whole class with advanced learners who sit next to elementary level student together. Obviously, many today's university classrooms are mixed-level classes since they have various language proficiency. Instructors teach learners with given university textbooks and materials which might not be suitable for the needs of all students. The fact is the teachers who use single instruction to the whole class might not get more productive results in a near future. In addition to utilizing a variety of teaching and assessment practices, differentiated instruction into lesson planning generally refers to a more effective approach to the current subject in accordance with the language proficiency of the learners. Impact of differentiated lesson planning to the class can produce more positive learners' performance and better understanding of the topic since the lesson plan is organized diversely. Obviously, differentiated lesson plan can later accelerate student engagement and more positive learning environment

since students feel more autonomy and self-reliance with better understanding of the topic. Learners may feel less secure in their language competence if they fail to comprehend the subject in comparison to their more experienced peers during the lesson. Providing different lesson plans beforehand can create more opportunities for both teachers and students to collaborate effectively during lessons and improving student engagement. Obviously, many educators can claim that preparing different lesson outlines might be time consuming, while the opponents prove the effectiveness of winning both time and comprehension of learning with diverse lesson outline for different learners in the classroom. Even in the primary class, for some the vocabulary activity can be fun while others struggle in it. Although it would seem like an appropriate teaching strategy to give the same lesson to the entire class, especially in a bigger class, not all students will succeed equally; those who don't likely to lose enthusiasm and inspiration for learning the language being taught [1].

Challenges and opportunities of differentiated lesson planning

First challenge is time management:

Teachers try to prepare their lesson plan according to their given study curriculum and learners' needs. There might occur great deal of challenges if they need to outline their lesson plan according to each learners' needs and level.

No	Student	Age	Current English level	Why are you learning English?	Which skill do you most want to improve?	What difficulties do you face when learning?	How do you prefer re to receive feedback?	What support are you waiting from instructors?
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								

9								
10								

The sample questionnaire table demonstrates seven questions which aid to identify learners’ level, their interest in the language, reason of learning, challenges they face during study. these questions assist teachers to create relevant activities which are focused mainly students struggling skills or level. Teachers providing these sorts of questionnaires or points, not least to scale learners’ needs and strongest sites, they can save more time to prepare more suitable lesson plan to the class accordingly. Teachers should not only understand but also identify learners’ needs while teaching them. However, not the quantity but quality is much more pivotal in academic sphere. For example, the lesson is based on technology-based activities and ten students out of thirty can manage advanced technology tools, while other twenty students struggle using basic gadgets during the lesson. Identifying these challenges aid both teachers and learners get on well with the lesson and improve their language competence. These approach not only help students to progress, teachers as well can improve their techniques to use multiple methods and approach.

Second challenge is classroom management difficulties:

The truth is that teachers may find it difficult to simultaneously manage hard assignments, resources, and activities for various needs and skill levels. There might be extra pressure to develop alternative lesson plans due to their level of skill (both novice and professional) and the university's limited resources. Teachers need to prepare both beginner and advanced levels adequate activities and instructions, which might be difficult for novice teachers if they have lack of experience. “Some student engagement and some student understandings are components of effective differentiated classrooms. They don't exhibit disorganization or lack of control.” [7] Teachers need to learn how to manage their classroom and keep students in control.

Moreover, university might lack of sufficient technology devises, materials and support for differentiated lesson plan preparation. These factors can be burden for less experienced ones. Tomlinson demonstrates that choosing which approaches to teach is crucial and that prolonged strategy, education sessions are more advantageous than shorter ones [6]. Notwithstanding the challenges, they need to ask for help from their advanced workers and try to use more needs assessment for learning to better focus their needs. Some teachers might not have adequate training in differentiated lesson planning and they need to be taught

how to use diverse instruction into one lesson plan. For lack of technologies and support from university, teachers should inform senior leadership positions and university administrators at a university. Language proficiency and subject knowledge are essential for language learners, just as knowing their own thought and learning processes helps them study well. Therefore, it would seem that teaching techniques for learning in a language classroom should take into account the variety of information and abilities that students possess. Additionally, planned teaching style should be tailored to the students' levels of understanding and application of learning strategies [1].

First opportunity is increased student engagement:

Differentiated lesson plan should be proactive [7]. Planning a single approach for everyone and then attempting to modify the plans when it becomes clear that the lesson isn't working for some of the learners for whom it is intended, effective differentiation is usually planned proactively by the teacher to be adequate to address a range of learner needs. Therefore, being proactive is demanded from teachers whom denying undifferentiated instructional planning. While gaining differentiated lesson plan, teachers can better meet learners' needs with addressing different learning styles, abilities and interest. Lesson plan dividing into diverse paths, lessons become more motivating and interesting since activities become more relevant for more students. Each lesson plan has its own learning objectives and it might be difficult to achieve all of them with different learners. With the help of differentiated lesson plan, more learning objectives can be accomplished. I have provided an example learning outcomes for vocabulary and reading focused lesson plan below. These objectives can address both beginner level (text and vocabs in an elementary level) and pre-intermediate level (intermediate level text is given)

- Demonstrate a positive attitude toward collaborative learning
- Participate actively during vocabulary activities
- Analyze the main ideas of the text with a group
- Create a presentation on the topic in a team

Meeting the objectives, lesson becomes more relevant and students feel more engaged. Differentiated lesson plan support learners to be active and be open minded during lesson. They can participate in role-plays, presentations without anxiety since they see they are being supported.

Second opportunity is professional growth:

Differentiated lesson plan can improve learners and teachers' professional growth. Since students who tend to work with lower-level groups for ages with

traditional approach cannot progress further. They see they have learned enough and need to take a rest while their lower-level peers are copying or asking a help form them. Despite the difficulties, learners who are being taught according to their level can learn more and become professional. According to Krashen's $i+1$ input theory, if students have access to a language that they can comprehend most of the time but have more grammar, vocabulary, and phrases than they are capable of understanding, they learn the target language most successfully. Input should be comprehensible and a bit difficult of the current level of learners, not too difficult and not too simple [4]. This statement is also appropriate to teachers: while teachers try to tailor learner needs, they also work on their academic performance with better preparation and better activities and materials. They try to develop their teaching skills in adaptive instruction and learners centered teaching rather utilizing teacher-oriented teaching methods. In order to meet multiple learners needs, teachers use multiple methods and techniques. This in turn, can bring great opportunities for teachers to become professional.

Differentiated instruction does not assume that every student is at a distinct level, even though it does provide multiple learning opportunities. Additionally, it emphasizes powerful concepts or meaningful learning for all learners. Moreover, many educators can assume that differentiated lesson plan means grading some easier, the others harder. They can give less difficult activities to weaker learners or providing more difficult materials for stronger students. However, this is totally a wrong assumption. Differentiated lesson plan in general prepare both students and teachers to be updated and more eager to learn new. Teachers need to be multitaskers in order to manage different activities for different learning groups, even some teachers can use grouping learners not with their level, but mixing them advanced with lowers. These organizations might be very effective to manage and aid lower-levels to be motivated and interested. Additionally, many individuals may believe that instead of employing one-size-fits-all instruction, teachers might multiply learners' homework with extra sources, yet addressing the right level and offering relevant materials are not time-consuming, however time-saving actually.

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